

An analysis of the European Industrial Carbon Management Strategy consultation: Who makes the normative decisions?

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Abstract

Establishing a framework for carbon management in Europe relies on collaboration between diverse actors. The European *Industrial Carbon Management Strategy* (the Strategy) is going through its last phase. As announced by the European Commission, the first quartile of 2024 will witness the deliberation of the Strategy. In the summer of 2023, a public consultation, and a call for evidence on the Strategy provided valuable stakeholder perspectives on the challenges and possible solutions for carbon management in Europe. This paper presents an analysis of these stakeholder perspectives and what input they give of the problems and solutions to carbon management. All submissions (n = 205) to the call for evidence were synthesised using qualitative system dynamics modelling. We found two dominant approaches to carbon management, a market-driven approach and a society-driven approach. Aligning carbon management within broader decarbonisation and fostering collaboration, requires a society-driven approach. A market-driven approach on the other hand provides high financial incentives. Our analysis suggests a conflict between a market-driven approach and collaboration, as a purely market-driven approach worsens the barriers to a collaborative approach, such as power and resource imbalance and a lack of facilitative leadership. Therefore, a careful balance between the two is required. This leads to several policy insights presented at the beginning of this paper.

Keywords: stakeholder perspectives; EU policy; CCS; CCU; system dynamics; Industrial Carbon Management Strategy; collaborative governance

Policy insights:

Insight 1: Most of the submissions to the consultation came from industry actors (the call for evidence 65.3%, the consultation 73%) resulting in a bias in the submissions towards industry perspectives. This should be kept in mind by the Commission as they consider the input they have received from the consultation.

Insight 2: A balancing between the market-driven and society-driven approach is required to ensure both the alignment of carbon management with the broader climate change mitigation and to foster a collaborative approach, while simultaneously providing financial incentives to carbon management. What is important to take into consideration in this balancing, is the question of *who makes the normative decisions on the role of carbon management and the direction of decarbonisation*.

Insight 3: Climate change and its mitigation through carbon management, is unavoidably a collaborative challenge due to the many interconnected challenges, goals, interests, solutions and the many stakeholders involved. The EU should take a strong facilitative leadership role to ensure this collaboration. This requires empowering less powerful actors and steering the direction of decarbonisation. The market-driven approach is based on a reductionist model of the 'social' in carbon management deployment and is unlikely to be able to alone take into consideration the more complex social aspects.

Insight 4: To help inform this more normative decision-making on the role of carbon capture in decarbonisation, public debate must be facilitated. Throughout the Industrial Carbon Management Strategy policy process, the consensus of the actors involved was that the time for debates on whether carbon

management technologies are necessary is over and now is the time for action. Comparison of this mentality to the findings from social sciences research on carbon capture indicates that this step may have been skipped completely and that many of the decisions being made now on carbon capture have never been debated with the public (Otto & Gross, 2021).

1. Introduction

In early 2024, the European Union (EU) is at the final stage of the development of the *Industrial Carbon Management Strategy*, a policy intended to be a key element of the wider policy framework for Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS), Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU), and carbon removals (Carbon Management technologies in rest of the paper) in Europe. This study examines the public consultation process the Strategy underwent in 2023.

Clear decisions on carbon management's role in European decarbonisation are crucial as the technologies face barriers and societal resistance while being expected to play a significant role in achieving climate targets (e.g. IEA, 2021). Yet, carbon management technologies already have a long history and have failed to take off despite times of significant interest (Arranz, 2016; IPCC et al., 2005). The EU member states have different political attitudes towards carbon management (CCUS Forum, 2023b), and so does the general public (Ashworth et al., 2019; Pianta et al., 2021; Steeper, 2013). It is not clear who will pay or take responsibility and bear the financial risks across the different steps. Adding to such complexity, information on the social considerations remain under-studied and under-appreciated in practice (Buck, 2021). Challenges in achieving social acceptance have resulted in delays and cancellations of projects (van Egmond & Hekkert, 2015), which shows the barriers social considerations can pose to developments when they are not given due consideration. More fundamentally, carbon management involves questions about the overall decarbonisation approach.

Complex challenges like carbon management are particularly hard to solve because they are tangled, hard to define, they have conflicting goals and demands and involve multiple stakeholders who each have their own interests (Rittel & Webber, n.d.; Schuitmaker, 2012; Torfing & Ansell, 2017). Collaboration is one effective way to respond to complex challenges as it brings actors together to achieve more than they could on their own (Ansell & Gash, 2008). Collaborative governance can lead to improved decision-making and policy implementation and fosters innovative solutions (Ansell et al., 2017). At the same time, the inclusion of actors with vested interests can also lead to the policy process being captured by interest protection instead of policy innovation (Torfing & Ansell, 2017).

Collaborative processes are influenced by existing relationships (Ansell & Gash, 2008). Significant power and resource imbalances can also impact collaboration, as the process faces the risk of being manipulated by more powerful actors (Ansell & Gash, 2008). Participants must have an incentive to participate, and key to this is whether the participants believe that the collaboration process could be meaningful (Ansell & Gash, 2008). Effective collaboration requires facilitative leadership (Ansell & Gash, 2008; Määttä, 2021; Torfing & Ansell, 2017) to steer the collaborative process and make sure the other requirements are fulfilled. Lastly, the rules and protocol (the institutional design) are crucial for the legitimacy of the collaborative process (Ansell & Gash, 2008). In addition, a series of factors are crucial for the collaborative process itself, including face-to-face dialogue, trust building, inclusion, and development of commitment and shared understanding (Ansell et al., 2020; Ansell & Gash, 2008; Siddiki et al., 2017).

Collaborative governance requires input from stakeholders to determine, and ultimately co-shape, the nature of problems and suitable solutions (Ansell & Gash, 2008; Kleantithis et al., 2022; Torfing & Ansell, 2017). In this paper, we analyse such input, the submissions to the call for evidence of the Strategy, available

through the European Commission policy consultation website¹. The analysis of the submissions focuses on answering the following questions:

1. *What barriers and enablers are raised in the European Industrial Carbon Management Strategy call for evidence by the stakeholders?*
2. *Whose interests were presented throughout the consultation and how does this impact the results of the consultation?*
3. *How can insights from the consultation process inform effective collaborative governance for carbon management in Europe?*

This study adopts qualitative system dynamics modelling (Meadows, 2008b) as a method to analyse the diverse stakeholder perspectives. This approach helps to manage the complexity arising from multiple stakeholder perspectives and provides a way to understand these in the broader system context (see e.g. Janipour et al., 2021; Mirchi et al., 2012). System dynamic modelling can also help to identify leverage points where interventions can have significant impact (Meadows, 2008a). By supporting a better understanding of the complexity of carbon management, the approach can contribute to effective policy decision-making.

The analysis resulted in two distinct approaches to carbon management: a market-driven approach and a society-driven approach. Broadly, the market-driven approach prioritises the acceleration of carbon management technologies as a standalone goal, while the society-driven approach views carbon management as a means to achieve the overarching goal of climate change mitigation. The analysis reveals that a market-driven approach may worsen barriers to collaboration.

The next section of the paper elaborates on the Strategy's policy process and the broader European framework for carbon management. Section Three will introduce the methods. Section Four will discuss the results of the analysis through qualitative system dynamics diagrams. Section Five will discuss the implications of the results. Lastly, Section Six will conclude the paper.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/13848-Industrial-carbon-management-carbon-capture-utilisation-and-storage-deployment/feedback_en?p_id=32161866 (accessed 30.10.2023)

2. Carbon management context in the EU

Consultations with stakeholders are vital in the EU policymaking process (Bunea, 2017; Labitzke, 2012). The European Commission employs consultations in policymaking to discuss draft policies or proposals with stakeholders such as member state representatives, interest groups, and concerned citizens in general (van Ballaert, 2017). The actors participating in policy consultations have significantly different levels of resources and influence. The European Commission, through its Directorate-Generates (DGs), sources advice from experts using various consultation methods i.e., conferences, workshops, expert groups, and online public consultations (van Ballaert, 2017). The Commission employs consultations as a useful tool for sourcing advice in the one hand, and for gaining attention and mobilising stakeholders' support for policy proposals on the other hand (van Ballaert, 2017). It is important to note that EU policy processes do not occur in a vacuum but rather in a complex context involving multiple levels, actors and both formal and informal processes (Wallace, 2005). Therefore, the consultation analysed in this paper is just one aspect of the policy process. (See the carbon management policy framework in the EU in Annex 1).

EU's carbon management framework development is progressing but facing critique due to slow speed (CCUS Forum, 2023a). The lack of inclusion of social considerations is particularly concerning as the current social sciences insights have not been adopted in practice (Buck, 2021) and the current discussions have had a strong acceptance focus, with limited attention given to other considerations such as justice (Swennenhuis et al., 2020; Upham et al., 2022), societal trust and participation (Otto et al., 2023; Porter et al., 2022; ter Mors & van Leeuwen, 2023). The importance of social acceptance has been recognised for carbon management due to it having caused delays or even cancellations of projects (Ashworth et al., 2012; van Egmond & Hekkert, 2015). As the broader social sciences insights remain under-appreciated (Buck, 2021), this raises concerns that more societal barriers will emerge or that the societal impacts of carbon management may be left un-recognised.

The context for the Strategy discussed in this section elaborates on some of the issues raised in the submissions and how these may be addressed in the final Strategy. Before moving onto the analysis of the consultation submissions, the next section explain the methodological approach adopted in the paper.

3. Methodology

Qualitative system dynamics modelling is a method that focuses on the causal relationships between different variables (Meadows, 2008b). By mapping these relationships, the modelling provides insights into the reasoning of the submitters, and the assumptions they have about how the structure of the carbon management system influences its behaviour. To foster transparency on the step from the submissions to the diagrams, the models are accompanied by citations from the submissions following suggestions in the system dynamics literature (Jalali & Beaulieu, 2023; Turner, 2023) (see Annex 2). Some interpretation on what to include in the models and what to leave out is necessary to warrant fruitful analysis. Therefore, issues were only incorporated in models if the frequency of the raised issue was high enough. In some cases, the plurality of views were summarised into more simplistic relationships in the models.

Our notation follows system dynamics standards (Meadows, 2008b). Each arrow represents a causal relationship, an arrow from variable A to variable B means that A is the cause and that B is the consequence. A plus arrow in the model refers to a relationship where the variables move in the same direction, an increase (decrease) in A leads to an increase (decrease) in B. A minus arrow on the other hand means that the variables move in opposite directions, an increase (decrease) in variable A resulting in a decrease (increase) in variable B. If there is a closed circle of causal relationships this constitutes a feedback loop, where a change in a variable leads via the other variables to a further change of that original variable. The feedback loops come in two forms. Reinforcing feedback loops amplify any change in the same direction, an initial increase (decrease) is followed by a further increase (decrease). Balancing loops dampen change because an initial increase (decrease) is followed by a change in the opposite direction, a decrease (increase). Reinforcing feedback loops are responsible for change and escalation, while balancing feedback loops are responsible for stability and inertia. A delay in change is represented in the models with two lines in the middle of an arrow.

The analysis was carried out in three steps:

1. The first step included an analysis of all the call for evidence submissions, and identification of their key features. These key features included the name and stakeholder category of the respondents, their key concerns, proposed solutions, and presented knowledge statements.
2. The second step focused on identifying connections between the stakeholder perspectives and arguments and the creation of qualitative system dynamic models based on this. In line with the system dynamics tradition, causal loop diagrams were used to map the causal mechanisms that were either explicitly mentioned in the submissions or implied in the reasoning. These causal diagrams help show visually which assumptions lead stakeholders to take certain viewpoints. The diagrams help to visually summarise and synthesise complex systems and worldviews.
3. The third step of the analysis focused on reflecting on existing literature to identify and analyse the implications and gaps of the qualitative system dynamics models. This resulted in the identification of policy recommendations based on the study.

The approach adopted in the present study is similar to how the method has been adopted in other studies related to carbon management technologies (Janipour et al., 2021). The models are a representation of the mental models and beliefs of the actors who provided a submission to the consultation, and as such do not necessarily represent reality. They present how the key stakeholders perceive the system to operate and are influenced by personal biases.

4. Results

The European Commission states that they received 278 valid feedback instances to the pre-specified questionnaire (European Commission, 2023b). For the call for evidence, they received 205 submissions. Only the submissions for the call for evidence are available publicly. As the participants were able to give their feedback more freely to the call for evidence, this data is better suited for qualitative analysis.

Industry views prevailed in the consultation (European Commission, 2023b) with approximately 65% of the submissions to the call for evidence coming from companies, businesses, and business associations. NGOs and citizens each provided 20 submissions (9.8%). The ‘others’ category included 13 submissions (6.3%). Academic and research institutions (including think tanks) provided 8 submissions (3.9%). Public authorities provided 6 submissions (2.9%). Environmental organisations provided 3 submissions (1.5%), and trade unions provided 1 submission. Most presented countries included Germany (27), Netherlands (17), Belgium (14), Finland (14), and Norway (12). A large majority of the submissions came from international organisations (43).

Various issues were raised in the submissions as obstacles to carbon management technology deployment. Table 1 summarises the main challenges raised in the submissions. The rest of this section will further explain what is meant by these, but first we will distinguish between two main approaches that help explain key positions that are taken in the submissions: the market-driven and the society-driven approach.

Table 1: Key challenges and responsibilities

Challenge	Raised often by	Relevant or Expected actor to take further action
Lack of a business case	Industry	Policymakers
Access to and development of transport and storage infrastructure	Industry and Civil Society Actors (NGOs, environmental organisations, citizens)	Industry and Policymakers
Limited attention to CCU compared to CCS	(CCU) industry	Policymakers
Overregulation	Industry	Policymakers
Lack of a clear regulatory framework	Industry, academic/research institutions, and NGOs	Policymakers
Responsibility/risk sharing	Industry	Industry and Policymakers
Lack of standardisation	Industry, academic/research institutions and NGOs	Policymakers
Concern over the alignment of carbon management with broader decarbonisation	Civil society actors and academic/research institutions	Policymakers
Concern over risks and societal costs	Civil society actors	Policymakers
Social acceptance	Industry and academic/research institutions	Policymakers (through awareness raising) and Society

4.1 Market-driven and society-driven approaches

Two distinct approaches can be identified from the debates surrounding the development of the Strategy, a market-driven approach and a society-driven approach. In some cases, the two approaches overlap, and they could be understood rather as a spectrum, but they are distinct in their approaches to regulation. The market-driven approach generally sees regulation as an obstacle to technology deployment, while the society-driven approach sees strict regulation as a necessary condition to make sure that technology leads to desired results. Another key difference between the approaches is how they perceive the role of carbon management (Figure 1). The market-driven approach tends to reason with carbon management as the end goal in mind. The society-driven approach, on the other hand, tends to reason with climate change mitigation as the end goal, and carbon management as one of several pathways to achieve this goal. The market-driven approach focuses on capturing carbon and has the tendency to view conditions and requirements as obstacles, while the society-driven approach sees the conditions and requirements as key to assure a harmony between different mitigation pathways. This difference helps explain substantial differences between the positions that are taken in the two approaches.

Figure 1: The role of regulations differs between a market-driven (reasoning in blue) and a society-driven (reasoning in green) approach.

Market-driven approach favours free carbon markets as the driving force for carbon management technology deployment. In this approach, the role of the EU is mainly restricted to enabling the market. The benefits of approaches that focus on economic considerations are seen to include cost-effectiveness and the ability to foster innovation (Sacchi et al., 2014; Sonneborn, 2004). Their weaknesses are seen to include the inability to create fundamental changes to the system and to decarbonise at the needed pace (Chaudhary, 2022) as capitalist firms are believed to be unable to absorb the financial losses implied by a rapid transition to net-zero (Adler, 2022). Market-driven approaches are also not believed to be enough on their own, but rely on policy support (Sonneborn, 2004).

The society-driven approach on the other hand focuses on careful steering of the market and carbon management through regulation. The integration of different climate mitigation goals, policies, and approaches is at the core of the society-driven approach (Biesbroek, 2021; Meijers & Stead, 2004).

“While it is crucial to define targets for available storage capacity, it is also important to ensure that a CO₂ storage target does not become an end goal in itself, risking the creation of perverse

incentives and/or failing to encourage other means of decarbonization where possible” (NGO submission)

In comparison to the market-driven approach, a society-driven approach imagines a system with greater government control and support. Some examples of what this can look like include the times of imminent crises such as World War II (Adler, 2022) and the COVID-19 pandemic (Ansell et al., 2021; Scognamiglio et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2022) (see also Määttä, 2021). This type of approach requires democracy to ensure legitimacy of the system, government support to incentivise innovation, and collective motivation (Adler, 2022). More fundamentally, a society-driven approach requires a move away from focus on cost-efficiency, as eco-efficiency is often not profitable (Adler, 2022). However, a society-driven approach can be considered as too ambitious and costly, and the public support in itself may not be enough to foster innovation.

Both the advocates for the market-driven as well as the society-driven approach argued for a clear regulatory framework as a crucial basis for carbon management deployment in the EU. Both also agreed on the necessity of collaboration to achieve effective carbon management in Europe.

What seems to be the preferred approach?

The two approaches are best understood as a spectrum, with most stakeholder perspectives positioning somewhere between the two approaches. The industry stakeholders commonly showcased a preference for a market-driven approach, but this was not always the case. Some key findings on the perspectives raised by the stakeholder groups include:

- Fossil fuel industry actors were most likely to argue for a free-market approach and to problematise restrictions. The reasoning for this is clear as the restrictions would exclude fossil fuel energy production with carbon capture as well as fossil fuel-based CCU.
- Companies and various business associations were very likely to problematise the lack of business models.
- Companies in favour of a society-driven approach elements accepted regulations that wouldn't affect their business activities or were too far in the future to impact current activities.
- NGOs and citizens were most likely to question the alignment and adoption of carbon management technologies in broader decarbonisation efforts.
- Academic/research institutions and public authorities did not show clear patterns in their submissions, but instead raised diverse views.

The consultation submissions steered more towards the market-driven approach, but both perspectives were presented. This was significantly impacted by the industry views being most dominant throughout the consultation. The preference for a market-driven approach is evident also in the CCUS Forum stance, which includes concern over regulation hindering the market (CCUS Forum, 2023c). Similar discourse was adopted by the European Commission's Director General ENER, Ditte Juul-Jørgensen, during the 3rd CCS Forum. What can be summarised from this is that the policy process faces strong advocacy towards a market-driven approach.

The following sections will discuss key elements of carbon management in Europe, as presented in the submissions. This dives deeper into the two approaches and the differences between them, as well as into the stakeholder perspectives. The analysis showcases that many of the decisions are normative. The rest of

the results section is divided into four themes, and under each theme, some relevant normative questions are highlighted.

4.2 Making the business case

The challenge of developing capture, transport, and storage capacity simultaneously is well-known in carbon capture discussions. The business case of both capture projects and transport and storage infrastructure projects relies on the existence of one another. Capture projects require the knowledge of where the CO₂ will be stored, how it will be transported there, and how much this will cost. Storage projects need a guarantee that they will have customers. CO₂ storage projects take a long time to develop, further complicating the challenge. This challenge is often called a ‘chicken-and-egg’ dilemma, but it can also be seen as a flywheel effect: an investment in the one encourages an investment in the others.

This positive reinforcing loop is further accelerated by the *learning effect*, as more projects will be developed, the developers will learn from these, and the costs will go down. The learning effect has been impactful for the acceleration of other technologies, such as renewables (de La Tour et al., 2013; Grafström & Poudineh, 2021). Previous research has highlighted that the strength of the learning effect depends on the technology and the causal mechanism can be more complex than that investment alone will lead to acceleration (Grafström & Poudineh, 2021). The learning effect for storage projects is expected to be lower than that of capture projects, because storage projects take longer and there are fewer projects to learn from. The learning and flywheel effect beliefs underlined the market-driven approach and the concerns over overregulation stifling the market.

“Currently, there is a lack of viable business models. Policies enabling the creation of a sustainable and viable market that would incentivise the private sector to invest in carbon management technologies must be implemented.” (Company/business submission)

The flywheel effect of capture, transport, and storage as well as the learning effects are visually summarised in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Flywheel and learning effects as the driving force of carbon management

Belief in the market-driven approach

“-- EU Commission should choose a path where “the best will not be the enemy of the good”.
(Business Association submission)

Concern about over-regulation was common in the submissions. This included an emphasis that temporary public funding is required to decrease the early mover risks and kick-start the market. The belief with this perspective is that the markets would be able to act self-sufficiently and the demand for public funding would decrease, resulting in overall societal (economic) costs being low with this approach. Uncertainty was another key challenge raised in the submission, which may negatively impact investor confidence and increase early-mover risks. This was followed by an emphasis that the role of the EU should be to provide regulatory certainty, which could be done for example by ensuring long-term certainty on the EU ETS price.

Some of the submissions argued that if the EU ETS price goes up too much and there is no easy access to affordable carbon capture, this will lead European industries to move outside of the EU. The CCUS Forum suggests that without affordable CO₂ transport and storage, companies will have no choice but to purchase ETS allowances, leading to increased costs and weakened financial capacity for decarbonisation (CCUS Forum, 2023a). What these arguments fail to consider, is that by design, as the EU ETS price goes up, this

creates an opportunity for other companies to make a business case for decarbonisation, resulting in overall progress on the European decarbonisation goals (Gerlagh et al., 2022). Thinking at the global level, if European industries move elsewhere in the hopes of avoiding stricter decarbonisation efforts, this is a significant risk to climate change mitigation.

CCU restrictions

Carbon utilisation is one possible way to make carbon capture profitable. Many of the submissions argued that the demand for carbon utilisation products should be supported and problematised policies that conflict with this goal. The regulations related to hydrogen and renewable liquid and gaseous fuels of non-biological origin (RFNBO) were problematised, as the regulation has become stricter on what is considered RFNBOs (Transport & Environment, 2023). RFNBOs are produced by using electrolysis powered by renewable electricity to produce Hydrogen (Transport & Environment, 2023). The hydrogen can be combined with for example nitrogen or carbon to produce ammonia or synthetic hydrocarbons (Transport & Environment, 2023). This carbon could be recycled carbon derived through carbon capture, providing an incentive for carbon capture and utilisation, but new regulations have put a 'sunset clause' for the use of carbon-based RFNBOs for 2041.

The new regulations exclude the use of carbon capture and utilisation to produce RFNBOs from 2041 onwards. Many of the submissions argued that the increasing role of hydrogen and RFNBOs in decarbonisation could be an avenue to support the business case for carbon capture through utilisation. Also the CCUS Forum has supported the case for CCU, by arguing for low-carbon hydrogen and that CO₂ remains an important feedstock (CCUS Forum, 2023a). Still, the European Commission's stance has been that the increase in hydrogen demand should be used to support further renewable energy generation and that the risk of increasing fossil fuel use should be avoided.

The business case model in Figure 3 below summarises the above and represents mainly the perspectives of those who advocate for the market-based approach and focus on economic considerations. Despite many of the arguments being streamlined, presenting clear statements on what the solutions should look like, several normative questions can be derived based on the model.

Normative questions:

- Who should steer the direction of decarbonisation and the role of carbon management in this?
- Who should benefit from carbon management and who should pay for it?

Figure 3: Making a business case for carbon management

4.3 Trade-offs of standardisation

The development of a European-wide CO₂ infrastructure is one of the key challenges for carbon management in Europe. Initially, carbon capture projects relied on full-chain business models, but now, more diverse models are emerging with multiple actors and cross-border collaboration (IEA, 2023, p. 10). This cross-value chain and cross-border collaboration requires coordination and shared rules. This has increased the complexity, but without collective coordination, there is a high risk of fragmented development. As the infrastructure must be shared, certain elements were emphasised as important criteria for this, such as third-party access, transparency, standardisation, and clear rules that are shared between the stakeholders (regulatory framework) (see also CCUS Forum, 2023d).

Submissions suggest that lack of information is a key barrier to utilising suitable storage locations across the EU. They propose that the Commission should mandate information sharing on possible storage sites. Some submissions also argue that exporting CO₂ outside of the EU should be made possible. The lack of ratification of the London Protocol is a key barrier to cross-border transport and storage arrangements. Current arrangements rely on bilateral agreements between countries.

Standardisation was emphasised as a particularly pressing issue. What was missing in these discussions was the possible trade-off with decreased flexibility. As standards are set in place, it is harder to change them as

technology develops. Flexibility is central to effective policymaking on complex challenges (Ansell et al., 2017). The importance of flexibility was recognised in the submissions but the impact standardisation may have on it was not.

“The development of an international standard for CO₂ specifications is essential and urgent to complement the regulatory framework for CO₂ transport, enabling the development of the CO₂ transport network in a safe, cost-efficient, interoperable, and accessible manner.” (advocacy group submission (other category))

The above is summarised in Figure 4 below. Here too the model helps derive normative questions that might otherwise remain unnoticed.

Figure 4: Standardisation helps international collaboration but reduces flexibility

Normative questions:

- Who should take leadership in the development of a European-wide CO₂ infrastructure?
- Who should be liable for the transport and long-term storage of CO₂?
- Who should fund and benefit from the CO₂ infrastructure development?

4.4 The relationship between renewable energy and carbon management

Many of the submissions emphasised that carbon management should be adopted only in cases where no other options to decarbonise are available (or economically feasible). Carbon management was recognised simultaneously as an essential solution to achieving net-zero but also as a risk to deeper decarbonisation as it may incentivise more fossil fuels or distract from other mitigation options. These perspectives emphasised the role of EU and member state facilitation in making sure these risks are avoided.

The relationship between renewable energy and carbon capture is manyfold. This relationship is often seen as carbon management taking investment away from renewable energy technologies (see also Climate Action Tracker, 2023; van Egmond & Hekkert, 2012). However, some of the submissions emphasised that the underlying argument for carbon management relies on the accessibility of affordable clean energy and that with the increasing demand for clean energy, the supply may not meet the demand. This perspective of carbon capture as another avenue for supporting renewable energy development has not been widely explored. Lastly, in some cases, the discussion on the availability of renewable energy was combined with

a discussion on the intermittent nature of renewables to argue for the use of carbon capture for fossil fuel electricity generation (Figure 5). The CCUS Forum highlights that Europe continues to have significant fossil fuel power production and new plants have been commissioned recently and some are under construction (CCUS Forum, 2023a).

Figure 5: Carbon management and climate change mitigation risks

4.5 Short-time products and CCU

As discussed earlier, some of the submissions problematised restrictions to the utilisation of captured carbon as this can negatively impact the business case for carbon capture. Here we go back to that line of reasoning. Research from de Kleijne et al. (de Kleijne et al., 2022) has showcased that only CCU that stores emissions permanently or which is made from zero-emissions energy is Paris Agreement compatible. The use of fossil fuel-based CCU for short-term products conflicts with climate change mitigation, as the emissions would be delayed (and only for a short term) instead of avoided (Figure 6). On the other hand, the submissions advocating for limited restrictions for CCU underlined their argument with the reasoning that due to the continuous demand for carbon as a feedstock, if this carbon is not recycled, virgin fossil fuel resources will be used instead. This was connected to the argumentation that the supply from biogenic and atmospheric CCU would not be sufficient to meet the demand for carbon feedstock.

“Indeed, we warn that this provision will block many planned projects and will be counterproductive in climate terms, harming severely the decarbonization strategies of whole branches of industry without offering alternative solutions.” (Business Association submission)

Figure 6: Will strict regulation on carbon management lead to better alignment with broader decarbonisation or will it lead to increased demand for virgin fossil resources?

Normative questions:

- Should support be extended to carbon capture in fossil fuel power generation?
- Under what circumstances should carbon capture be prioritised over alternative decarbonisation strategies?
- Should carbon management technologies be transitional technologies or long-term solutions?

4.6 Reductionist understanding of the social considerations

The social considerations relevant for carbon capture are often seen in a reductionist way, the complexity of these issues reduced to a belief that lack of social acceptance is the core problem and that this can be mitigated through knowledge provision (Figure 7). Social scientists have attempted to bring more nuance into the discussion (Buck, 2021; de Coninck, 2013; Otto et al., 2023), but this nuance has not been adopted in practice. Moreover, social scientists have critiqued the deficit framing approach and assumptions that a lack of knowledge causes a lack of acceptance (Ahteensuu, 2012; Brunsting et al., 2013).

The reductionist model is intertwined with the market-driven approach, as the legitimacy of this approach relies on diminishing the relevance of social issues, and the allocation of responsibility over them to the industry. The market-driven approach largely represents the industry perspective on carbon management, which focuses on economic considerations. From the industry perspective, broader societal considerations are not a priority, and the social considerations are often limited to those that directly impact the success of

projects. Lack of social acceptance has in many cases led to delays and cancellations of projects (van Egmond & Hekkert, 2015), which explains why the importance of this one social consideration is recognised over others. The industry perspectives on what are considered important social considerations for carbon management have been often taken for granted, which emphasises the responsibility of other actors to bring broader societal considerations into the discussions.

Figure 7: A reductionist understanding of the social

Trust

The submissions which discussed the more extensive social considerations were rare. Only 10 of the 205 submissions included a discussion on social considerations beyond social acceptance and awareness, and often this discussion was left short. These other social considerations included issues such as trust, social costs, value sharing, engagement, public debate, and justice. Trust has been a growing topic in social sciences discussions on carbon capture (Otto et al., 2023; Porter et al., 2022; ter Mors & van Leeuwen, 2023). Trust was raised as a topic in the submissions by an EU-project C4U. This submission represents the more comprehensive discussion on social considerations beyond the acceptance paradigm, emphasising that not only social acceptance but also societal trust on the justness of the transition is crucial for effective deployment of carbon capture technologies. The work of the C4U project is used here to illustrate a broader understanding of the social dimension of carbon capture (Figure 8).

The C4U project (Porter et al., 2022) emphasises that society will support CCUS only if the transition is just and if it trusts the industry. Government on the other hand depends on the legitimacy of CCUS policies. Industry places its importance on the business case, as is evident also from the analysis of this paper. What this simple model showcases, is that fairness and trust are important steps in supporting carbon management implementation, and focusing merely on acceptance is not sufficient, as it cannot be achieved without a broader understanding of what the relevant social considerations are. The model shows that societal support,

industry commitment and governmental action are strongly interrelated and cannot be seen as separated from each other.

Figure 8: C4U project model (Porter et al., 2022)

Normative questions:

- Should we engage the wider society on the direction of decarbonisation or should we aim at informing them about the changes and their necessity?
- Should the benefits of carbon management be shared with the wider society?

5. Discussion

The analysis of this paper resulted in the identification of two approaches to carbon management in Europe, a market-driven approach, and a society-driven approach. The two approaches have significantly different consequences for carbon management. Many of the relevant decisions are normative and require selection between different goals and values. With the market-driven approach, the decision-making would be left to economic considerations which are unlikely to fully cater to the interests of the wider society. Still, an economic incentive is a key element in motivating industries to participate in climate change mitigation. Therefore, a careful combination of the two approaches is recommended.

Section 4.5 highlighted an underdeveloped understanding of why social considerations are relevant for carbon management. Many actors' beliefs align with the reductionist model, where the focus is on social acceptance and public awareness, while considerations such as societal trust, participation, and justice are ignored. This persistence of the reductionist model shows a significant risk that social concerns may be underestimated or not recognised. Somewhat ironically, broadening the understanding of the role of the public in carbon management, and dropping the focus on 'acceptance' may result in greater 'social acceptance' of carbon management. More collaborative approaches have led to less adversarial policymaking, and recognising the importance of societal trust has a positive impact on the relationships between actors.

Collaborative processes are impacted by relationships, imbalances in power and resources, incentives to participate, facilitative leadership, and institutional design (Ansell & Gash, 2008). Effective collaboration requires face-to-face dialogue, trust building, inclusion, and shared understanding (Ansell & Gash, 2008). Previous experiences with social acceptance, project delays and cancellations, and high interest with little success have impacted relationships among carbon management actors. Current attempts to collaborate cross-border face struggles due to non-ratification of the London Protocol. The EU can play a facilitative role to mitigate power imbalances, but the two approaches have varying impacts on collaboration effectiveness. The market-driven approach may increase imbalances and leave less incentive for non-industry actors to participate.

Trust: As showcased by the social considerations models, the role of trust in carbon management is at risk of being disregarded. This can have a significant negative impact on the effectiveness of the collaborative processes as trust is a precondition for effective collaboration. Moreover, societal trust is crucial for sustainability transitions and net zero (Otto et al., 2023).

Inclusion and face-to-face dialogue: The consultation process included open participation, but these processes are not public-friendly. They include complicated language and the public is often not aware when these consultations take place.

Commitment and shared understanding: Most of the stakeholders appear to be committed to the development of carbon management, but the process is hindered by a lack of shared understanding. The collaborative process requires clear decisions on the role of carbon management in climate change mitigation. Many of the decisions on this role remain open, as emphasised by the normative questions highlighted throughout the results section. This increases uncertainty among the stakeholders on what types of carbon management will be welcomed and supported.

Moreover, the results of the analysis relate to debates on the effectiveness of market-driven approaches to climate change (Jones, 2011; Sonneborn, 2004). Our analysis suggests a conflict between a market-driven approach and collaboration, as a purely market-driven approach worsens the barriers to collaborative

approach, such as power and resource imbalance and a lack of facilitative leadership. This leads to several policy insights presented in the beginning of this paper.

6. Conclusions

We argue that carbon management requires collaboration across the value chain, countries, and society. We analysed the consultation process for the European Industrial Carbon Management Strategy and identified two approaches to carbon management in Europe- market-driven and society-driven. An effective approach requires balancing between the two approaches.

The limitations of the study include the lack of direct stakeholder contact, which may have resulted in some considerations being left outside of the scope of the study. The selected method of system dynamics modelling also includes some limitations, the selection of variables always includes leaving some variables outside the scope of the study. The selection of variables was explained in the methods section. The lack of direct contact with the stakeholders and the impact of this was mitigated with extensive background work of the authors, including participation in the Commission events surrounding the consultation.

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During the preparation of this work the authors used Grammarly AI in order to shorten and improve the readability of the text. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no personal or financial conflicts of interest to declare. However, it is important to note that Moises Covarrubias Perez and Vincent de Gooyert are actively involved in the C4U project, which provided a submission to the policy consultation analysed in this paper. While Senni Määttä conducted the analysis independently and is not directly associated with C4U, the involvement of Moises Covarrubias Perez and Vincent de Gooyert in the C4U project may be perceived as a potential conflict of interest. We believe that their participation in the C4U project does not compromise the integrity and objectivity of the analysis presented in this paper.

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Annex 1. European Carbon Management Framework

Document	Description
The Directive on the geological storage of CO ₂ (CCS Directive) CCS Directive (European Commission, 2009)	The CCS Directive establishes a regulatory framework for the development and operation of geological carbon dioxide (CO ₂) storage in the EU.
The London Protocol	The London Protocol is an international treaty that regulates the disposal of products at sea, aiming to effectively control marine pollution. This includes CO ₂ streams. In 2009, the Protocol was amended to allow for cross-border transportation of CO ₂ for sub-seabed storage, but the amendment must be ratified by two thirds of the contracting parties to enter into force, and this has not yet taken place. A further resolution in 2019, allowed for provisional adoption of the 2009 amendment before it comes to force. Two or more countries can now agree to transport CO ₂ for sub-seabed geological storage.
The Green Deal Industrial Plan (2023) (Commission, 2023)	The Green Deal Industrial Plan was published in February 2023, and it sets ambitions for the green transition of Europe’s

	industry. The plan identifies carbon capture technologies as some of the key products to achieve climate neutrality.
EU Green Deal	The European Green Deal, approved in 2020, is a set of policy initiatives by the European Commission with the overarching aim of making the European Union climate neutral in 2050.
The Net-Zero Industry Act	The European Commission proposed the Net-Zero Industry Act on 16 March 2023. The Act is part of the Green Deal Industrial plan and its goal to provide a predictable and simplified regulatory environment. The Act aims to promote investment in net-zero technologies, such as carbon management technologies. The Act is one of the measures introduced to help deliver on the goals of the Fit For 55 and REPowerEU objectives. REPowerEU is a European Commission proposal to end reliance on Russian fossil fuels before 2030 in response to the 2022 Russian invasion of Ukraine.
Fit For 55 legislative package	Under the European Climate Law, the EU has committed to reduce its net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030. The Fit for 55 package aims to make all sectors of the EU's economy fit to meet this target. As a part of this legislative package, the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) has been reformed.
The EU Emissions Trading System (ETS)	The EU ETS is the EU's is a carbon emissions trading scheme which began in 2005. It works on a 'cap and trade' principle. Emitters are given emission allowances, which decrease over time, aligning with climate goals. If the emitters emit more than their allowances permit, they must buy more allowances on the EU Carbon Market or through trading with other companies or pay fines.
EU Strategy on Energy System Integration	The EU strategy on energy system integration aims at linking the various energy carriers, electricity, heat, cold, gas, solid and liquid fuels, with each other and with the end-use sectors, such as building, transport or industry. This linking-up also includes CO ₂ infrastructure.
Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism	The Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism is a carbon tariff on carbon intensive products, such as cement and some electricity, imported by the European Union. The mechanism takes effect in 2026.
Commission Communication on Sustainable Carbon Cycles (European Commission, 2000)	In December 2021, the Commission published a Communication on Sustainable Carbon Cycles that outlines EU-wide actions to scale up carbon farming initiatives and industrial solutions in order to sustainably capture, store and recycle carbon. The Communication discusses the need to recycle carbon from sustainable biogenic sources for industries which will continue to be reliant on the use of

	carbon. It also discusses the need for carbon removal technologies to achieve climate targets.
EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework Proposal (COM/202/672) (EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework Proposal, 2022)	In November 2022, the Commission published a proposal for a Carbon Removal Certification Framework. The Framework aims to promote carbon removal solutions, and to establish a carbon certification system to avoid greenwashing.
Trans-European Networks for Energy (TEN-E)	The Trans-European Networks for Energy (TEN-E) is a policy that is focused on linking the energy infrastructure of EU countries.

Annex 2. Citation examples for each of the relationships in the diagrams

Relationship	Citation example
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strictness of regulation ->(+) harmonisation of climate change mitigation approaches • Harmonisation of climate change mitigation approaches -> (+) climate change mitigation (Mt avoided/year) 	<p><i>“While of crucial importance, CCS is no silver bullet. [redacted] targeted use is key.”(NGO submission)</i></p> <p><i>“ [redacted] would again like to repeat that the different potential for climate impacts from CCS and CCU, with the latter’s climate impact being highly variable. This must be taken into consideration when determining where the public’s support and where funding is best placed to foster market development in a manner consistent with the climate crisis.” (NGO submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strictness of regulation -> (-) carbon capture (Mt/year) 	<p><i>“However, The CO2 market is still at a very early stage and as such does not require a full fledged regulatory framework beyond what is already provided in the CCS directive. “ (Company/Business submission)</i></p> <p><i>“[redacted] stresses the need to align current EU-legislation (e.g. on nature) with our common challenge for a swift decarbonization of our economies, allowing large-scale CCS projects to be realized swiftly in the EU (for example by granting certain exemptions in permitting procedures for net-zero technologies as CCS).” (Company/business submission)</i></p> <p><i>“We cannot afford to be ideological about technologies and their use; the earlier CCS technologies start being deployed at scale, the faster we will start storing large quantities of emissions and reducing costs. That is why CCS-related policies should aim at facilitating investments and at helping CCS become an option for decarbonization, rather than restricting beforehand its</i></p>

	<i>use and room for deployment.”(Company/business submission)</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon capture -> (+) climate change mitigation (Mt avoided/year) • Carbon capture projects -> (+) CO2 mitigation • Emissions -> (-) climate change mitigation (Mt avoided/year) 	<p><i>“The science is clear that carbon dioxide removal (CDR) – alongside a strong prioritization on greenhouse gas emissions reduction – is “unavoidable,” and will be required at gigatonne (Gt) global scale by 2050 to reach net zero and have a chance to limit warming to 1.5 or even 2°C. “ (Business association submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attractiveness of transportation and storage of CO₂ -> (+) investment in transportation and storage capacity • Investment in transportation and storage capacity -> (+) transport and storage capacity • Transport and storage capacity -> (+) attractiveness of capturing CO₂ • Attractiveness of capturing CO₂ -> (+) investments in capture capacity • Capture capacity -> (+) Attractiveness of transportation and storage of CO₂ 	<p><i>“As noted by the [redacted], accelerating CCUS is a “chicken and egg” problem. Transport and storage operators will not invest unless they have binding CO2 volumes from emitters, who in turn will not invest in capture technology without access to transport and storage.” (Other category submission)</i></p> <p><i>“The main barrier to CCS development is first and foremost the lack of available CO2 storage and transport infrastructure, which in turn discourage investments in carbon capture technologies.” (Company/business submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost reduction transport and storage through learning -> (-) cost of transport and storage • Transport and storage capacity -> (+) experience with transport and storage • Cost reduction capture through learning -> (-) cost of capture • Capture capacity -> (+) experience with capture • Experience with capture -> (+) cost reduction capture through learning • Investments in capture capacity -> (+) capture capacity 	<p><i>“As a ready to scale-up technology, public support through provision of incentives and development of robust regulatory frameworks could allow corporates to claim removals and further catalyse financing for the accelerated deployment of the technology, thereby stimulating cost reductions associated with economies of scale.” (Company/business submission)</i></p> <p><i>“That is why, at first, Europe should focus on supporting those projects that can be deployed faster and more cost-efficiently – which will depend largely on location and various technical factors – so that they can pave the way for cost reduction, infrastructure build-up and scale-up of the technology. Once those low-hanging fruits have been picked and costs reduced, it will be easier to apply CCS to those industries for which it is harder to do so today.” (Company/business submission)</i></p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost of capture -> (-) business case • Cost of transport and storage ->(-) attractiveness of transportation and storage of CO₂ • Cost of capture -> (-) attractiveness of capturing CO₂ 	<p><i>“CCS has the potential to be a great decarbonisation solution for Europe while protecting its industry and preserving jobs; but for CCS to be able to be deployed at scale, costs need to be brought down.” (Company/business submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attractiveness of capturing CO₂ -> (-) companies moving outside of the EU • Companies moving outside of the EU -> (-) climate change mitigation 	<p><i>“For Europe to remain on track to its climate objectives, while preserving the competitiveness of its industry, a marked shift in approach is needed towards more technology-inclusive, competitiveness-oriented, and less prescriptive policymaking.” (Business Association Submission)</i></p> <p><i>“Certain industries, e.g., cement, lime, steel, or glass production, emit CO₂ not related to the combustion of fossil energy. CCUS is the key solution to mitigate process related emission from these industries allowing them to continue operating in the EU.” (Business Association submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restrictions on the use of fossil fuel based carbon utilisation -> (-) demand for CCU products • Demand for CCU products -> (+) attractiveness of carbon utilisation • CCU -> (+) business case for carbon capture projects • Attractiveness of carbon utilisation -> (+) attractiveness of capturing CO₂ 	<p><i>“It is imperative to assess precisely what would be the impacts of a general sunset clause for the use of industrial CO₂ in 2040. In France, and probably in the rest of Europe, the major entries into service for production projects of synthesis molecules are planned in 2027-2028. These projects need to work at least 15 years, rather 20 years, to amortize their investments. Therefore, a sunset clause on December 31, 2040, is just equal to stop immediately the investment decisions and to block the projects.” (Business association submission)</i></p> <p><i>“The current EU framework endangers ongoing and planned CCU investments. For instance, the decision to no longer consider CO₂ emissions put to use in Renewable Fuels of Non-Biological Origin (RFNBO) as being avoided from 2041 is not justified and should urgently be reviewed. These rules result in cutting off a CO₂ supply without assessment of the availability of CO₂ from biogenic sources and DAC to respond into the CO₂ industrial needs.” (Business association submission)</i></p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strictness of carbon management regulations -> (-) attractiveness of capturing CO₂ 	<p><i>“To maximize their value, carbon management solutions should not be envisaged only as a last resort to mitigate residual industrial emissions; but also, as an efficient solution to reduce other sectoral emissions, decarbonize flexible power generation, enable the production of low-carbon hydrogen needed to fuel the industries of tomorrow, and to achieve negative emissions when combined for instance with bioenergy.” (Company/business submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strictness of carbon management regulations -> (+) climate change mitigation 	<p><i>“The ICMS should treat CCS on its own as a transitional means of addressing emissions from certain industrial activities to be used in certain cases. There are certain instances when CCS can have significant greenhouse gas mitigation potential and can be integrated into existing industrial processes and activities, whilst avoiding significant negative side effects and fossil fuel lock in.” (NGO submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strictness of carbon management regulations -> (-) investor confidence 	<p><i>“The certification process needs to be technology neutral and open for all carbon removal options available to ensure that no viable solution is excluded. Under the current proposed definitions, it is unclear whether capture and storage of the biogenic CO₂ from waste-to-energy would be eligible.” (Company/business submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU ETS price (+) business case 	<p><i>“However, rising carbon prices including ETS, lower technology costs and the development of a mature CCS market, are likely to lead to a balance between ETS cost savings and the costs of CCS-gained CO₂ reductions. At least for emitters whose emissions are all part of the ETS system.” (Public authority submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Temporary public funding to initiate the market -> (-) cost of capture • Temporary public funding to initiate the market -> (-) uncertainty 	<p><i>“In the initial phase, public funding, coupled with coordinated infrastructure planning, will be necessary for the development of CO₂ transport and storage infrastructure, while de-risking policies will be crucial to empower private players to kickstart the deployment of CCS.” (Company/business submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertainty -> (+) early mover risk • Early mover risk -> (-) investor confidence • Investor confidence -> (+) business case 	<p><i>“In that sense, the development of a regulatory framework for Carbon transport and storage faces a number of the challenges that e.g. the roll-out of next generation fibre networks and hydrogen networks have also faced recently in that regulators need to provide a framework that incentivises the build-out of new infrastructure in the presence of volume risk, which in this case can be understood as uncertainty about the overall economic</i></p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk reduction -> (+) business case 	<p><i>viability of the infrastructure (as opposed to year-on-year demand fluctuations).” (Company/business submission)</i></p> <p><i>“Current ETS prices are not sufficient to drive the not-yet established CCS value chain. This means that first movers in any part of the value chain will need to take disproportionate risks.” (Public authority submission)</i></p> <p><i>“It also refers to enabling and introducing barrier-reducing policy instruments, which the European Commission’s Industrial Carbon Management initiative can facilitate to create the requisite ambitious conditions to reduce project risk through clarity and regulatory certainty, which will drive projects towards implementation. This is why Aker Carbon Capture first and foremost, calls for support and incentives that rewards actors who move first to decarbonize.” (Company/business submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardisation and interoperability -> (+) transparency 	<p><i>“A robust and consistent GHG accounting is necessary to avoid gaps and double counting. In order to promote innovation towards avoiding emissions and even removing CO2 from the atmosphere, there should be clear rules on monitoring and accounting in ETS and non-ETS sectors. The objectives should be that all CO2 is accounted for, including transfers and that double counting and/or double crediting is avoided.” (Company/business submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transparency -> (+) effective coordination 	<p><i>“In addition to CO2 capture and storage activities, Member States should be obliged to provide information on national and international transport needs and activities to assist in coordinating ‘source – sink’ matching across the Union and third countries.” (Company/business submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective coordination -> (+) collaboration between countries 	<p><i>“Although various EU member states have already signed MoUs on cross-border transport (like the Netherlands and Belgium), [redacted] sees an active role for the European Commission as well in improving the legal and policy frameworks for cross-border CO2-transport and promoting cross -border cooperation.” (Company/business submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration between countries -> (+) cross-border infrastructure 	<p><i>“Furthermore, we encourage the EU and its Member states to collaborate closely to align as far as possible the</i></p>

	<i>requirements for financial security site operators must provide across Europe as well as the regulatory framework for handover of liability of stored CO2.” (Academic/research submission)</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-border infrastructure -> (+) CO₂ mitigation 	<i>“The future of an efficient low carbon economy relies on the development of CO2 infrastructure networks.” (Company/business submission)</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardisation and interoperability -> (+) providing certainty and predictability • Providing certainty and predictability -> (+) risk reduction 	<p><i>“More clarity on the rules would significantly help to accelerate the development and use of CO2 storage in Europe. The ICMS could also introduce a regime of CO2 transport and storage go to areas to help speed up the permitting process in individual member states or as part of cross border projects.” (NGO submission)</i></p> <p><i>“This creates a different set of challenges, as this shared infrastructure will need to aggregate multiple CO2 sources and end-uses (whether utilisation or storage), which requires harmonised specifications and standards, as well as a robust model for sharing risks and liabilities, which should not fall solely on the public sector.” (Academic/research submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business case -> (+) carbon capture projects • Business case -> (+) attractiveness of capturing CO₂ 	<i>(one of two main challenges to carbon capture technologies): “Lack of market mechanism: Legal security is needed to encourage investments in CCUS technologies, but an adequate policy framework is currently missing.” (Company/business submission)</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective policies -> (+) CO₂ mitigation 	<i>“Developing an integrated and coherent EU strategy for CCUS through a decentralized principle – the strategy should address elements relevant to cross border (standards, quality, and trade) while allowing flexibility for Member States to develop national strategies, markets, and structures.” (Public authority submission)</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investment in carbon management technologies -> (-) investment in other mitigation options • Investment in other mitigation options -> (+) climate change mitigation (Mt avoided/ year) 	<i>“In 2009, we created a website dedicated to CCS, where we analysed a wide range of issues related to CCS: timing (in the climate context), environmental impacts, climate impacts, economics, financing, liability, relationship to energy scenarios and CDM/JI, among others. These analyses led us to conclude that CCS could not be considered a viable climate tool, but rather a tool of interest to the coal, oil and gas industry</i>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investment in other mitigation options -> (+) share of renewable energy in the system • Low regulation carbon management (e-fuels, other short lifetime CCU products, fossil sources of carbon) - > replacement of renewables or other more sustainable options 	<p><i>and the energy companies - and countries - with large fossil fuel interests.” (NGO submission)</i></p> <p><i>“In the lead up to 2030 we should invest in all the green technologies such as solar panel production, wind turbines and renewable hydrogen for targeted sectors to reach the 2030 climate goals. CCS cannot and should not be put on equal footing with existing alternatives already proven to significantly cut carbon emissions and phase out fossil fuels.” (NGO submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share of renewable energy in the system -> (+) intermittency of energy supply • Intermittency of energy supply -> (+) investment in energy generation from fossil fuels with carbon capture 	<p><i>(CCS is required to...): “complement the role played by renewable technologies in the power sector; by introducing in the power mix a clean dispatchable energy resource able to maintain the adequacy and the reliability in a decarbonized electricity system” (company/business)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investment in energy generation from fossil fuels with carbon capture -> (-) climate change mitigation (Mt avoided/year) 	<p><i>“For instance, CO2 streams captured from fossil fuel sources or whose technologies depend on the continued use of fossil fuels will undermine the decarbonisation potential that these technologies represent for the sector.” (Company/business submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attractiveness of carbon utilisation - > (+) CCU 	<p><i>“Companies with industrial CO2 sources are not supported today to install carbon capture plants dedicated to CCU because CCU (except for CO2 permanently bound by mineralization) is not accepted as emission abatement in the ETS. When the resulting CCU product is not accepted as "green" or "sustainable" without a sunset clause even if required CO2 certificates are submitted, it is unlikely that a CCU company will pay for the CO2. Therefore, investments in CCU value chains are not incentivized today, even though they could lead to an overall CO2 reduction in the short term.” (Other category submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short lifetime carbon products -> (+) attractiveness of carbon utilisation 	<p><i>“Carbon is an important component in many products, and today most of that carbon comes from fossil sources. There is, however, not enough non-fossil carbon available for companies and other stakeholders to use in their production, as a result of the lack of investment in CCUS technology and the lack of a well-functioning transportation network for captured CO2. Favourable conditions and rules could facilitate and accelerate the development of new CCUS technologies, which could help</i></p>

	<i>to mitigate emissions and contribute to more sustainable production of carbon-based products.” (Company/business submission)</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short lifetime carbon products -> (+) emissions 	<i>“Carbon removals will play an indispensable part in reaching the EU’s climate neutrality goal for 2050. Hence it is urgent that carbon is supported by an appropriate policy framework that needs to be developed. At the same time, achieving negative CO2 emissions by carbon removals must not in any way replace or reduce the efforts to mitigate emissions by phasing out fossil fuels.” (Business association submission)</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restrictions on the use of fossil fuel based carbon capture and utilisation -> (+) use of virgin fossil resources • Use of virgin fossil resources -> (+) emissions • Low regulation carbon management (e-fuels, other short lifetime CCU products, fossil sources of carbon) -> replacement of virgin fossil fuels with recycled carbon and e-fuels 	<i>“Being aware that only a limited and insufficient amount of renewable energy as well as renewable hydrogen is available it should be noticed that with this limited amount of renewable energy and renewable hydrogen more fossil based chemicals and fuels can be replaced by using CO-containing process gases compared to CO2 based processes.” (Other category submission)</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strictness of regulation -> (-) low regulation carbon management (e-fuels, other short lifetime CCU products, fossil sources of carbon) • Carbon lifetime of CCUS -> (+) climate change mitigation • CCU in low lifecycle products -> (-) carbon lifetime of CCUS • Restrictions on the use of fossil fuel based carbon utilisation -> (-) CCU in low lifecycle products 	<p><i>“When using CO2 capture and utilisation (CCU), i.e. the use of new fuels and materials, it must be ensured that carbon dioxide is not released back into the atmosphere, even after ideally repeated use. CCU should therefore be limited to the use of CO2 from the air.” (translated from Germany, NGO submission)</i></p> <p><i>“Once the carbon is captured, a long-term storage must be guaranteed by permanently storing carbon in geological formations. The conversion of carbon to products with a short lifetime, such as e-fuels, should not be accounted for.” (NGO submission)</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strictness of regulation -> (+) strict carbon management (permanent storage, biogenic and atmospheric sources of carbon) 	<i>“It is important to envisage CCS only after the other options have been considered, not as a default. CCS should not delay the urgent need to reduce emissions at the source. For certain industrial sectors other options are now available. This will maintain the incentive to reduce emissions at the source over end-of-pipe technologies.” (NGO submission)</i>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strict carbon management (permanent storage, biogenic and atmospheric sources of carbon) -> Climate change mitigation (Mt avoided/year) 	<p><i>“The overarching goal of the energy and climate policy should be to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Thus, the CCUS strategy should outline policies and support mechanisms that allow the use of CCUS only in the case of emissions that are impossible or economically unprofitable to avoid, so that the possibility of installing CCUS does not provide an incentive, e.g. to build new generation capacities based on fossil fuels.”</i> (Academic/research submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness raising campaigns -> (+) public awareness • Carbon management in Europe -> (+) public awareness 	<p><i>“Improving social acceptance of CCS projects will require more efforts from EU and MSs in disseminating and sharing information, including technical ones, on CCS needed role in the decarbonization process.”</i> (Company/business submission)</p> <p><i>Implied that familiarity will increase awareness.</i></p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public awareness -> (+) social acceptance of carbon management technologies 	<p><i>“To what extent the much needed public support will be awarded to CCS projects in the long-term, in a predictable manner reducing investment risks and foster market development, depend on public support and awareness of the technology.”</i>(NGO submission)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social acceptance of carbon management technologies -> (+) carbon management in Europe 	<p><i>“Derisking also means that the upcoming CCUS strategy should pivotally address public awareness and acceptance - this is crucial in the development of CCUS projects in territories.”</i> (Company/business submission)</p>